

SMART SENSOR BASED ON THE IEEE 1451 STANDARD FOR MONITORING COASTAL AREAS SENSITIVE TO FUEL LEAKAGE

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ABSTRACT

Oriented to detect and classify fuels in coastal areas, a methodology for designing a smart sensor device, based on the IEEE 1451 standard and decision tree, is presented in this article. The physical elements of the proposed device are sensors for signal acquisition, and a microcontroller for processing, classification and communication. The software elements of smart sensor are the classification algorithm and communication protocol. Signals captured by the sensors include hydrogen potential, turbidity, temperature, pressure, location and colors. The microcontroller process these signal that are used to detect and classify the presence of polluting fuels in the water. Additionally, the smart sensors are encapsulated to prevent damage caused by the deteriorating characteristics of fuels. For monitoring and evaluation purposes, the signals/data and classifications are sent to a cloud using Internet of Things (IoT) techniques, and monitored using ThingSpeak®. The performance of the smart sensor was evaluated in the laboratory using appropriate materials. The measurement and classification tests were conducted using containers with solutions of water and fuel.

KEYWORDS: Smart Sensor, IoT, Decision Tree, Online Monitoring, Fuel Oil And Petroleum Product.

I. INTRODUCTION

Oil spills are catastrophic events for the environment, known mainly for the event of stains found on the Brazilian coast that were not identified at their origin. They are mainly caused by ship spills, fractures in ducts and drilling operations in inappropriate locations [1]. Taking into account that oil slicks spread quickly and cannot be extracted once they become too thin, typically only 20% of the total amount of oil is recovered in a spill [1] [3] [4] [5].

Studies show that knowing the type of oil and its thickness in different locations, in the first minutes after the spill occurs, reduces the cost of recovery, as it helps to indicate the most efficient treatment route [5]. This is because the response can be planned more efficiently while containing the effects of pollution [4].

Measurement techniques using physical contact instruments, compared to current techniques, are more resistant to environmental conditions and more reliable for different types of pollutants. While remote sensing, mainly synthetic aperture radar (SAR, synthetic aperture radar) and techniques that use fluorosensor lasers, which are the most common techniques, present several disadvantages such as delay in response time, high cost, It depends a lot on the environment, light, temperature and sea conditions [6] [7].

Spill areas are often difficult to access due to the presence of hazardous chemical materials, potential explosion and fire risk, and represent sensitive areas for environmental monitoring. The arrival of pollutants in such areas can trigger significant changes in the local ecosystem, especially when it comes to coastal regions. Faced with these challenges, it is possible to explore remote sensing as a valuable

tool to obtain detailed information about the occurrence and magnitude of these events. This approach allows for a more accurate and safer analysis, contributing to the understanding and efficient response to environmental accidents [8] [9].

In this way, monitoring using a smart sensor to detect pollutants is an important step towards protecting the marine environment [10]. This article aims to assemble a smart sensor based on standard 1451, which measures water quality indices sensitive to accidents involving fuel. However, the use of similar systems should not replace other detection methods, but rather add to a better and more complete marine monitoring system.

II. STATE OF ART

For the development of this work, a state of the art is used as a basis, which directly involves the development of methods based on software, equipment and techniques for intelligent monitoring of pollutants in degraded coastal regions.

In [11], a conception and implementation of an embedded system for Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN) is proposed with the aim of preventing and mitigating the environmental impact of oil and its derivatives' transportation and extraction. The proposed system is a static sensor node that utilizes machine learning and IoT to detect and classify pollutants in aquatic environments. Divided into three phases, the development of the sensor node includes the conception and modeling of the system, implementation of the static sensor node, and detection and classification tests in indoor environments. The effectiveness of the sensor node, assessed through satisfactory experiments with seawater samples and pollutant tests, positions it as a promising device for the detection and classification of pollutants in real-world aquatic environments.

In [12] an agricultural environment is monitored through a network made up of smart sensors. Each smart sensor measures temperature, humidity, luminance, atmospheric pressure, water level and soil humidity, and then this data is processed in order to evaluate the designated region of each sensor. After processing, all smart sensors send their data to a server, which in turn sends it to a database, where it can be analyzed later.

Similarly, [13] uses a smart sensor to monitor environmental parameters such as temperature, humidity, pressure and sunlight. Processes such as error correction are carried out on the data and, finally, this data is sent to a cloud, where it can be accessed remotely.

In [10] a smart sensor composed of a photo-ionization sensor is used to detect the presence of hydrocarbons in solutions containing mixtures of water and fuels such as gasoline, diesel, ethanol, etc. An artificial neural network was implemented in smart sensor in order to classify whether the solution was very, reasonably or not very concentrated. This data was then sent to a central computer for viewing and storage.

In [14] they presented the detection of oils through their spectral signatures using smart sensors. Using multispectral techniques, it is possible to determine the type of oil through the ratio between the wavelength and the absorbance spectrum of the oil. However, the spectrum range varies according to the seawater and the spectral quality of the incident light [15].

III. SMART SENSOR DESIGN

To design the smart sensor, the IEEE 1451 standard must be followed, which determines and characterizes smart sensors. This standard describes a set of interfaces for connecting instrumentation systems, transducers with microprocessors and [11] networks. It also introduces the concept of a Transducer Interface Module (TIM) that contains interfacing, signal conditioning, analog-to-digital and/or digital-to-analog conversion and, in many cases, the [16] transducer. The main steps of the methodology for developing the smart sensor are seen in Figure 1.

3.1. Sensor development methodology

Figure 1. Steps of the methodology for developing the smart sensor. The smart sensor project is divided into 5 stages, which are 1) signal acquisition, 2) signal processing and classification, 3) communication, 4) cloud storage and finally 5) monitoring via software and mobile devices.

The first stage of signal acquisition consists of studying the parameters to be measured, in order to be able to measure those using sensors, and transform this measurement into a value with a common reference. These parameters are hydrogen potential, temperature, turbidity and pressure. This data set allows us to proceed to the second stage.

In the second stage, signal processing and classification are carried out, where the presence of pollutants in the solution is detected. Firstly, the data measured in the first stage are processed by smart sensor and then based on reference values it is possible to determine whether or not there is the presence of a polluting fuel in the aquatic environment.

In the fourth stage, this is where the data is stored. After the data is sent in the third step, it is stored in a cloud. This data can then be viewed and monitored in the fifth stage, using software.

3.2 Signal acquisition

To acquire the signals, it will be necessary to understand the parameters that will be measured and observed. Parameters are principles through which it is possible to establish a comparison. Therefore, fuel parameters are analyzed in order to compare them and determine which fuel is present in a given solution.

3.2.1. Parameters observed for measuring petroleum derivative compounds in water

To assess the quality of beach waters, criteria established in CONAMA Resolution No. 274 approved on November 29, 2000, establishes criteria for bathing Brazilian waters, classifying them into categories based on the presence of fecal coliforms to guarantee public health. and environmental protection. The waters are monitored monthly and classified as suitable (excellent, very good, satisfactory) or unsuitable for primary contact recreation [17]. The results of the analyzes must be disclosed in a way that is accessible to the public, with information made available on visible signs in recreation areas. The resolution makes environmental and public health bodies responsible for monitoring and protecting bathing areas, ensuring the safety of recreational activities and the preservation of water bodies. The parameters to be observed are:

- A. Water pH - The measurement and control of pH in marine environments are essential for ecosystem health, physiological processes of organisms, and the economic and social sustainability of coastal communities. pH alterations directly influence the health of corals,

phytoplankton, and other vital marine organisms, impacting the food chain and biodiversity. Ocean acidification, resulting from CO₂ absorption, poses a growing threat, compromising the reproduction, growth, and homeostasis of marine species. Additionally, detecting the presence of fuels in the water, which also causes pH changes, is crucial for identifying contamination. The introduction of fuels can cause significant pH variations, indicating pollution and necessitating rapid interventions. Therefore, monitoring pH not only preserves environmental health and local economies but also serves as an alert system for the presence of hazardous pollutants, allowing for effective mitigation actions [17];

- B. Water temperature- in marine environments play a crucial role in understanding and preserving marine life, as well as protecting coastal ecosystems. Water temperature is one of the primary environmental factors that directly influence the health and dynamics of marine communities. Variations in temperature can affect the physiological, behavioral, and reproductive processes of marine organisms, from the simplest to the most complex, impacting the entire food chain and ecosystem structure. Additionally, early detection of contaminant presence, especially petroleum derivatives, is paramount for marine ecosystem health. The introduction of these contaminants into the water can significantly alter thermal properties, causing abrupt changes in temperature and compromising the survival and reproduction of sensitive organisms. Therefore, continuous temperature monitoring is essential not only to assess environmental conditions and the functioning of marine ecosystems but also to provide valuable information for the management and conservation of these vulnerable environments;
- C. Turbidity - Measuring turbidity in marine environments plays an essential role in assessing water quality and understanding the processes that govern the dynamics of marine ecosystems. Turbidity, as a measure of the amount of particles suspended in water, not only influences light penetration, crucial for phytoplankton growth and photosynthesis, but also plays a key role in the distribution and availability of essential nutrients. Variations in turbidity can directly affect the survival and health of marine organisms, impacting biodiversity and the structure of coastal ecosystems. Furthermore, water turbidity can be a sensitive indicator of pollution events, such as fuel spills at sea. These spills pose a serious risk to marine life and the health of ecosystems, as the presence of oils and chemicals can not only increase water turbidity, but also directly contaminate and harm marine organisms, with long-term impacts on biodiversity and productivity of marine ecosystems. Therefore, continuous monitoring of turbidity is essential not only for understanding marine ecological processes, but also for early detection and mitigation of adverse impacts of pollution events, such as fuel spills, on marine ecosystems [17].

3.3. Signal Processing and Communication

The signal processing and classification stage is carried out using the ESP32. The software allows the processing of measurements taken, in order to keep them more stable and less sensitive to environmental changes. By processing the data, it is possible to use it to classify and determine what type of solution is being analyzed.

The last 3 steps in Figure 1 are linked. Communication between the sensor and the network is used to store data in the cloud, where this data can be accessed for monitoring. The communication channel deals with the transmission of signals through measurements from sensors present in the smart sensor structure. After taking measurements and processing the signals, the data is sent to a server via a wireless network connected to the internet, to store, receive and visualize the processed signals.

IV. MODELING AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE EMBEDDED SYSTEM OF THE SMART SENSOR STRUCTURE

This Section presents the smart sensor prototype, experimental tests and their respective results and discussions of the proposed methods. Comparisons of results obtained between theory and physical experiment are also carried out.

4.1 Smart sensor structure

The structure, data acquisition, processing and power supply of the smart sensor. This device is a sensor capable of detecting and classifying fuels present in aquatic environments and sending the data to a cloud in order to monitor them. It was designed in accordance with the IEEE 1451 standard, in order to contain all the necessary parts so that it maintains all the characteristics of a smart sensor. Each part of the proposed sensor is related to items 1), 2) and 3) in Figure 1. Figure 2 shows the components used to develop the smart sensor.

Figure 2. Components used for the development of the smart sensor.

The structure, data acquisition, processing and power supply of the smart sensor. This device is a sensor capable of detecting and classifying fuels present in aquatic environments and sending the data to a cloud in order to monitor them. It was designed in accordance with the IEEE 1451 standard, in order to contain all the necessary parts so that it maintains all the characteristics of a Smart Sensor. Each part of the proposed sensor is related to items 1), 2) and 3) of Figure 1. Figure 2 shows the components used to develop the smart sensor, the item is 1) ST-100 turbidity sensor, 2) Waterproof DS18B20 temperature sensor, 3) BMP 180 pressure and temperature sense, 4) ph4502c pH sensor, 5) GY-NEO6MV2 GPS module, 6) Tcs230 color Detection Sensor, 7) ESP32, 8) Lm2596 Step down regulator, 9) 2200 mAh Li-Po battery.

The prototype of the proposed smart sensor is simulated via Fritzing software, and its structure is shown in Figure 2, electrical circuit of the node composition. The smart sensor is made up of 6 sensors (the color sensor is unfeasible, it was noticed during usage tests, in practice 5 sensors were used), 1 microcontroller, 1 battery and 1 voltage regulator. The smart sensor is designed to operate in aquatic environments with the purpose of detecting and classifying the presence of combustibles in seas and rivers. Its internal part is encapsulated so that the electronic components (shown in Figure 2) do not come into contact with liquids, only the part of the liquid contact sensor probes. The structure was developed considering the criteria of buoyancy and friction with waves on the sea/lake/river surface.

Figure 3 shows the encapsulation structure of the electronic part, modeled in SolidWorks software, which allows you to simulate the structure virtually, the fittings between the platform (in gray) and the Styrofoam box (in blue). Measurements of the length, height and width of the box are used to simulate, facilitating the sizing of the platform.

Figure 3 – Encapsulation structure of the smart sensor node simulated in SolidWorks: (a) perspective view and (b) bottom view of the structure.

The proposed structure was designed to allow the passage of the three water contact sensors (1, 2, 4 shown in Figure 2), immersed in the solution so that it is possible to carry out pH, turbidity and temperature measurements, thus detecting and classifying the presence of fuel and water. The proposed structure was designed to allow the passage of the three water contact sensors (1, 2, 4 shown in Figure 2), immersed in the solution so that it is possible to carry out pH, turbidity and temperature measurements, thus detecting and classifying the presence of fuel and water. With the first tests carried out via software, the smart sensor was implemented, with the project ready, the support part for the water contact sensors was printed using a 3D printer and Lactic Polyacid (PLA) material. Then this part was attached to a Polystyrene thermos with a volume of 5 liters, the prototype is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 - Structure of the smart Sensor: (a) in perspective, in its composition there are 3 water contact sensors and further to the right it is possible to see a fourth sensor which is the color sensor, (b) lateral and (c) bottom: structure undergoing functional test, it is noticeable to see the operation of the color sensor, which proved to be unlikely to be viable for applications in contact with liquids, even though it was waterproofed with resin, its use in the final tests was not viable.

In Figure 4 show the proposed smart sensor in 3 perspectives, the choice of polystyrene was due to its mechanical resistance in small tidal fluctuations for first tests, buoyancy and its impermeability, thus being ideal for tests carried out in a simulated environment.

4.2 Signal processing and classification

The processing and classification of the signals presented in this section and referring to step 2 of Figure 1, for the physical processing of the signals and to house the classified, the ESP32 microcontroller was chosen, which has in its structure a chip with two 32-bit cores, Wi-Fi connections -fi 802.11b/g/n (2.4 GHz) with a range of approximately 20 meters and Bluetooth 4.2, it has a low-power coprocessor that can work independently, saving energy when less intensive tasks are being performed.

The smart sensor performs 10 measurements, with each cycle 10 samples are collected. The pre-processing logic works as follows, the algorithm excludes the largest and smallest measurements, and finally the remaining values are averaged. With the resulting values, the smart sensor performs the classification and sends the results and measurement signals to ThingSpeak®. The program flowchart of the smart classifier based and decision tree is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 - Flowchart of the measurement, detection and classification process of the decision tree-based smart sensor.

The classification algorithm presented in flowchart format in Figure 5 is inspired by the decision tree method, which is a machine learning method used for classification and regression. In the first step of the algorithm, the difference between the environment temperature and the temperature of the liquid is checked. If the difference is greater than 1°C, it is assumed that there is a considerable amount of fuel in the solution. In the next step, the values resulting from turbidity and pH measurements are evaluated according to the following information, for Gasoline its turbidity is from 2.36 to 2.42 NTU and pH from 6.5 to 7, the turbidity value of diesel ranges from 2.30 to 2.32 NTU and pH 6 to 6.5.

Following the flowchart in Figure 5, it can be seen that if the sensors perform erroneous measurements and the sensors indicate the presence of fuel, but indicate different fuels, the classifier understands it as an erroneous measurement, and determines the result as inconclusive. After that, the smart sensor will repeat the measurements to be sure of the fuel present.

4.3 Smart sensor consumption

To choose the battery, the consumption of each sensor was measured so that the battery could be sized. The calculation of the general consumption of the smart sensor was based on the individual consumption

of each sensor based on its technical specifications in the respective technical sheets, however this consumption is carried out taking into account a single sensor. As the smart sensor uses several sensors and functions, the circuit consumption was measured. The measurement was carried out using a multimeter and a bench power supply, the experiment is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6- The smart sensor consumption measurement test.

Figure 6 shows the consumption test of the proposed embedded system, the highest measured consumption of the smart sensor was 270 mA for each measurement, a 2200 mAH battery was used. To adjust the voltage between the battery and the circuit, a Step Down Lm2596 voltage regulator was used. The battery was connected to the regulator, the output voltage was 3.3 V, which is the supply voltage for the sensors and the microcontroller. It is worth mentioning that the consumption was not always 270 mA, this consumption was only recorded when all the sensors were performing measurements and the microcontroller processed the signals and sent the data. The maximum consumption time is due to measuring and sending signals within the 15 second interval that the smart sensor takes to perform measurements and send the measured signals to the cloud.

4.4 Communication, storage and monitoring

The communication structure is the third stage shown in Figure 1, the generated processed signals and data are sent to a cloud/server, where they are stored and allow sensor signals and classification to be monitored online.

The platform/server chosen for this work was ThingSpeak®, which is a web server, which receives real-time data transmitted via the ESP32's wireless connection. ThingSpeak® has an Application Programming Interface (API) that allows the visualization and processing of collected data directly in the MATLAB® software and via its web page.

The ThingSpeak® is an online IoT platform that allows you to visualize and store data in real time in the cloud. Once the data is stored in ThingSpeak®, it can be accessed from any device with internet access. It is also possible to create channels, where each channel has two application programming interface (API) keys, thus allowing a user to only be able to send data to that channel if they have the writing API key, and only be able to download data from the channel if has the read API key. It is also possible to choose whether the channel will be private or public, determining whether it is possible for other people to also view the fields of a given channel.

To monitor the signals generated by the smart sensor, a channel was created with 8 fields for the following parameters: turbidity, pH, liquid temperature, environment temperature, pressure, latitude, longitude and classification.

The acquired signals are sent to a Message Queue Telemetry Transport (MQTT) which is an online server responsible for receiving data. MQTT has several advantages, including cloud storage that prevents data loss when there is a loss of connection or sensor failure. Another advantage is that the stored data can later be extracted into XML-type table formats that can be interpreted by any data analysis software (SILVA et al., 2019).

V. LABORATORY TEST RESULTS

In the laboratory, 2-liter polyethyl terephthalate (PET) bottles cut in half were used to place the mixtures. In one of the bottles, 200 ml of water and 100 ml of gasoline were mixed, while in another bottle, 200 ml of water and 100 ml of diesel were mixed, as can be seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7-Tests carried out in the laboratory - Bottles with diesel and gasoline fuels.

Using the PET bottles with the mixtures in Figure 7, the smart sensor reading and its classification algorithm were tested. Then, the smart sensor was tested to send the reading data and the classification was carried out by it to Thingspeak®.

5.1 Smart Sensor Tests

The smart sensor measurement and classification tests showed satisfactory results regarding turbidity, pH, environment and liquid temperature, pressure and location. The tests are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 - Measurements: (a) Diesel and (b) Gasoline.

These measurements are between the values presented in Figure 5, therefore the classification indicated in the last line (gasoline) is satisfactory and matches the fuel being measured. The classification results in the Arduino IDE are presented in Figure 9 where a) gasoline classification and b) diesel classification.

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COM9
Location: Lat: -2.558873, Lon: -44.307788 Sat: 8 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 15:55:57.00
Location: Lat: -2.558873, Lon: -44.307788 Sat: 8 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 15:55:57.00
Location: Lat: -2.558873, Lon: -44.307788 Sat: 9 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 15:55:57.00
Gasolina
-----
R= 21  G= 23  B= 18
-Measurement 15
NTU: 2.39
pH Val: 6.50
Temp liquid: 30.62 graus C
Temp Environmental 31.70
Pressure 1005.40 hpa
R= 21  G= 22  B= 18  | Branco

Location: Lat: -2.558872, Lon: -44.307787 Sat: 9 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 15:55:59.00
Location: Lat: -2.558872, Lon: -44.307787 Sat: 9 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 15:55:59.00
Location: Lat: -2.558872, Lon: -44.307787 Sat: 8 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 15:55:59.00
Location: Lat: -2.558872, Lon: -44.307787 Sat: 8 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 15:55:59.00
Location: Lat: -2.558872, Lon: -44.307787 Sat: 8 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 15:55:59.00
Gasolina
-----

COM9
Location: Lat: -2.558856, Lon: -44.307730 Sat: 7 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 16:01:15.00
Location: Lat: -2.558856, Lon: -44.307730 Sat: 7 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 16:01:15.00
Location: Lat: -2.558854, Lon: -44.307731 Sat: 7 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 16:01:18.00
Location: Lat: -2.558854, Lon: -44.307731 Sat: 7 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 16:01:18.00
Diesel
-----
R= 20  G= 21  B= 17
Measurement 24
NTU: 2.32
pH Val: 6.03
Temp liquid: 30.50 graus C
Temp Environmental 31.60
Pressure 1005.40 hpa
R= 20  G= 22  B= 17  | Branco

Location: Lat: -2.558856, Lon: -44.307749 Sat: 7 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 16:01:20.00
Location: Lat: -2.558856, Lon: -44.307749 Sat: 7 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 16:01:20.00
Location: Lat: -2.558856, Lon: -44.307749 Sat: 7 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 16:01:20.00
Location: Lat: -2.558856, Lon: -44.307749 Sat: 7 Date/Time: 12/14/2021 16:01:20.00
Diesel
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Figure 9- Smart sensor measurement and classification for a) gasoline, b) diesel.

In Figure 9, the values for latitude and longitude are accurate, as in addition to indicating that the Smart Sensor is in the city of São Luís, the values are precisely indicating the location of the LCP at UFMA. It is also noted that the time values are 3 hours ahead. This is due to the fact that the sensor adopts the time in relation to Greenwich Mean Time (GMT), which is measured through the London observatory, which in turn has a time zone of +3 in relation to the city of São Luís. However, measuring colors is not satisfactory for classifying fuels. In the tests carried out, the color sensor reading should be something close to pink when measuring gasoline and yellow when measuring diesel. However, it can be seen that it is returning a white reading. This difference is due to the fact that measurements are being carried out in liquids, and therefore not all incident rays from the color sensor are reflected, enabling correct reading of the photodiode array. In liquids, part of the light rays are reflected and the rest are refracted. As part of the rays are refracted, there is a loss of information and therefore the color sensor does not identify the pinkish color of gasoline or the yellowish color of diesel.

5.2 Testing sending data to Thingspeak

After the detection and classification tests, data sending and classification tests were carried out to Thingspeak® to monitor the data in real time. Data was sent every 15 seconds. The index monitoring graphs are displayed in Figure 10, the values of turbidity, pH, environment temperature, liquid temperature, relative pressure at sea level, longitude, latitude and classification.

Figure 10 - Monitoring measurements in real time.

In Figure 10, there is a greater variation in the room temperature measurements than in the liquid temperature measurements. This happens because the tests were carried out in a refrigerated environment, so the room temperature sensor captured a more abrupt change than the sensor positioned in the solution. On the other hand, a small difference is noticed in the two temperatures, and this difference is important to detect the absence or presence of fuels. In Figure 10, there is a greater variation in the room temperature measurements than in the liquid temperature measurements. This happens because the tests were carried out in a refrigerated environment, so the room temperature sensor captured a more abrupt change than the sensor positioned in the solution. On the other hand, a small difference is noticed in the two temperatures, and this difference is important to detect the absence or presence of fuels. The turbidity and pH measurement values are slightly high, this is due to sample contamination. As the liquid temperature, turbidity and pH sensors are inserted directly into the fuel solutions, they must be cleaned after use. As the turbidity sensor works through the luminance received by the photodiodes, soap can cause these higher readings by preventing luminance reception. While the pH sensor measures more basic values, as mixing water with soap produces a basic solution.

The Figure 10 presents measurements of relative sea level pressure. The relative pressure remains practically stable at around 1005.48 hPa, which is an acceptable average. The sea level pressure of São Luís according to the Government Portal is on average 1014 hPa. This difference between the average and the measured value is due to the 5% error of the sensor and also to the fact that the relative pressure

takes into account the environment temperature, the higher the temperature, the lower the calculated relative pressure.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a smart sensor project was proposed capable of detecting and classifying the presence of fuels in aquatic environments in addition to sending them to the cloud. To this end, turbidity, pH and temperature sensors were used to detect and classify, while sensors such as GPS and pressure were used in order to know the current position and relative pressure of the sea level where the Smart is located. Sensor. There were also sensors such as color sensors, which despite being capable of differentiating color frequencies, were not able to identify the color of the fuels tested, as this sensor does not work with raw measurements in liquids. To send the measurements and classification to the cloud, and also assist in monitoring, the ThingSpeak® software was used.

It was possible to verify the efficiency of the smart sensor based on tests carried out in the laboratory using seawater and fuels such as gasoline and regular diesel. The smart sensor was able to detect the presence of fuels in the solution, in addition to identifying which fuel was present. It was also able to send the measurements taken and the classification to ThingSpeak®, so that the measurements can be monitored from any device with internet access.

Sea simulation tests were not possible due to lack of time, so the smart sensor does not have results that can prove its efficiency at sea. However, the laboratory results indicate a good probability that the Smart Sensor would have positive responses to tests in simulation of water bodies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. JERNELÖV, "The threats from oil spills: now, then, and in the future," *AMBIO 39 Springer*, pp. 353–366, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-010-0085-5>, 05 July 2010.
- [2] A. Jernelöv, "The Threats from Oil Spills: Now, Then, and in the Future," *Ambio -Springer*, pp. 353-366, Jul 2010.
- [3] ITOPI, "Response marine oil spill. Whitherby & The International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation," PROMOTING EFFECTIVE SPILL RESPONSE, Londres, Reino Unido, 1986.
- [4] M. Fingas e C. E. Brown, "A Review of Oil Spill Remote Sensing," *Sensors*, vol. 1, n° +, p. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s18010091>, 2017 December 2018.
- [5] S. B. O. Szewczyk, "Processos envolvidos em um derramamento de óleo no mar," FURG, Rio Grande, RS, 2006.
- [6] H. Denkilkian, A. Koulakezian, R. Ohannessian, M. S. Chalfoun, M. . K. W. Joujou, A. Chehab e I. H. Elhadj, "Wireless sensor for continuous real-time oil spill thickness and location measurement," *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement* , pp. 4001 - 4011, December 2009.
- [7] O. Ejofodomi e G. Ofualagba, "Crude Oil Spill Detection Using Robotic Systems," *EJERS, European Journal of Engineering Research and Science*, vol. 4, n° 12, pp. 112-116, 2019.
- [8] A. H. S. Solberg, "Remote Sensing of Ocean Oil-Spill Pollution," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, pp. 2931 - 2945, 2012.
- [9] O. B. Gonzalez e J. Chilo, "WSN IoT ambient environmental monitoring system," em *IEEE 5th International Symposium on Smart and Wireless Systems within the Conferences on Intelligent Data Acquisition and Advanced Computing Systems (IDAACS-SWS)*, Dortmund, Germany, 2020.

- [10] A. TONACCI, D. Corda, G. Tartarisco, G. Pioggia e C. Domenici, “A Smart Sensor System for Detecting Hydrocarbon Volatile Organic Compounds in Sea Water,” *CLEAN–Soil, Air, Water, Wiley Online Library*, p. 147–152.
- [11] Y. F. d. Silva, J. V. Fonseca Neto e R. C. S. Freire, “Conception and Design of WSN Sensor Nodes Based on Machine Learning, Embedded Systems and IoT Approaches for Pollutant Detection in Aquatic Environments,” *IEEE Access*, pp. 117040-117052, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3325760, 18 October 2023.
- [12] G. R. MENDEZ e S. C. MUKHOPADHYAY, “A wi-fi based smart wireless sensor network,” *Wireless sensor networks and ecological monitoring-Springer*, pp. 247-268, 2013.
- [13] M. HAEFKE e H. EWALD, “A zigbee based smart sensing platform for monitoring,” em *IEEE International Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference*, Hangzhou, China., 2011.
- [14] R. D. SCAFUTTO, C. R. FILHO e W. J. OLIVEIRA, “Hyperspectral remote sensing detection of petroleum hydrocarbons in mixtures with mineral substrates: Implications for onshore exploration and monitoring.,” *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing, Elsevier*, p. 146–157, 2017.
- [15] J. Blink, “Boundary tracking and estimation of pollutant plumes with a mobile sensor in a low-density static sensor network,” *Urban Climate- Elsevier*, vol. 14, n° 3, pp. 383-395, 2015.
- [16] IEEE, “Standard for a Smart Transducer Interface for Sensors and Actuators—Common Functions Communication Protocols and Transducer Electronic Data Sheet (TEDS),” 2007. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/stamp/stamp.jsp?tp=&arnumber=4338161>. [Acesso em 14 ju 2024].
- [17] BRASIL, “Resolução CONAMA n° 274. 2000,” 2000. [Online]. Available: https://www.icmbio.gov.br/cepsul/images/stories/legislacao/Resolucao/2000/res_conama_274_2000_parametrosambientaisqualidadedasaguas.pdf. [Acesso em 10 jun 2024].
- [18] P. F. Kingston, “Long-term environmental impact of oil spills,” *Spill Science & Technology Bulletin*, pp. 53-61, 2002.
- [19] T. I. T. O. P. F. (ITOPF), “Oil Tanker Spill Statistics 2019,” 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.itopf.org/knowledge-resources/data-statistics/statistics/>. [Acesso em 25 setembro 2020].
- [20] H. Denkilian, A. Koulakezian, R. Ohannessian, M. S. Chalfoun, M. K. W. Joujou, A. Chehab e I. H. Elhajj, “Wireless Sensor for Continuous Real-Time Oil Spill Thickness and Location Measurement,” *IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement*, vol. 58, n° 12, pp. 4001 - 4011, 2009.

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